

AP Capstone Research Project

**Improving Language Learning Through Subtitles: Investigating the Role of Bimodal Input
Through the Lens of Cognitive Theories**

Word Count: 4732

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in international interest in entertainment content, specifically dramas. Dramas combine compelling visuals with engaging dialogue; the increase in drama interest internationally created a rise in interest in foreign language dramas, notably K-dramas (Korean dramas) and Thai dramas. According to Hye-Jin Kim and Seok-Jin Cho, they recorded that interest in dramas correlated with a 60% increase in learning the Korean language among Vietnamese youth (Kim & Cho, 2024). Similarly, studies show how Thai drama viewing increased significantly and how that led to a rise in interest in Thai culture (Ko, [2022](#)). Noting this interest in foreign language learning, it has become increasingly more important to find the most efficient way to actively learn a language.

Learning a language combines both the motivation of the learner and the actual skill of learning the language (vocabulary and comprehension). Due to the increasing popularity of foreign dramas (and the ability of dramas to combine visual and audio aesthetics of a language), dramas are gaining support as a language instruction tool, due to improving motivation and encouraging language learning. More specifically, when watching dramas, the presence of subtitles is noted to improve comprehension and vocabulary retention, while simultaneously keeping student motivation high. However, while subtitles can be beneficial in a language learning aspect, there are concerns of increased cognitive load with subtitles and doubts regarding the benefits of subtitles on an audience unfamiliar with the language.

In order to effectively assess the value of subtitles, it is important to understand the cognitive theories behind developing language skills and how this process can be optimized with entertainment content. Dual Coding Theory (DCT), introduced by Paivio, assumes “that human

cognition in reading and writing depends on dual coding systems of mental representations”; one coding system (verbal system) deals with verbal representation and the other coding system (imagery system) deals with non-verbal representations. Multimedia Learning Theory (MLT), introduced by Richard Meyers, stems from the possibility of learning with content that is multimedia (has more than one medium of communication) and utilizes three assumptions to state that learning is more efficient with visuals and language than just from language (Wei & Fan, [2022](#)). The present study uses a quasi-experimental research method on high school students in central Orlando (Florida) to assess the impact of subtitles on vocabulary retention of the Thai language and comprehension of a Thai drama scene, in relation to cognitive learning theories.

Literature Review

1.1 Foreign Language Learning Rise

In recent years, the interest in foreign language learning has increased exponentially, largely fueled by the easy access to various foreign entertainment content online through streaming platforms and social media. For instance, the increasing popularity of K-dramas and Korean culture has sparked a phenomenon of Hallyu, or the Korean Wave, amongst various parts of the world (namely the West and Southeast Asia). When observing the impacts of this phenomenon and its effect on local youth, Hye-Jin Kim and Seok-Jin Cho discovered that increase in available content and the interest of youth in consuming Korean content consequently

related to their interest in the Korean culture and learning the Korean language (Kim & Cho, [2024](#)). Similarly, when looking at the impact of Chinese media on Chinese learning students, Anjana and others observed that watching dramas not only impacts comprehension and vocabulary retention but also boosted the motivation of the learners, supporting the theme that increasing content accessibility improves the interest in learning the associated foreign language (Anjana et al. [2024](#)). These studies support the point that increasing the availability of foreign language content facilitates the use of entertainment content as an informal teaching tool for language learning.

1.2 Importance of Language Learning

Research has consistently shown that language learning is beneficial not only for communication but also for improved cognition and academic performance. Cambridge, a reputable U.S. University, highlights a meta-analysis that stated "majority of studies (90%) showed that language learners perform better across a range of academic subjects than students who don't study a second language" and found that "early studies on language learning found evidence that it boosted learners' empathy". Aside from the social and academic benefits, language learning also significantly boosts cognition, as it boosts memory (Spence, [2022](#)). Learning vocabulary for a secondary language requires boosted cognitive abilities (specifically recall) and increased memory, supporting the crucial role that second language learning has in improving the well-being of learners.

The Thai language is unique in its characteristics because of its complex tonal quality and written characters (very different from the English language script). Thai consists of five tones that influence the meanings of words, making understanding these tones crucial in acquiring Thai

vocabulary. Furthermore, Thai consists of significantly more consonants (44) and vowels (18) than English, making understanding this language require both visual and auditory comprehension (aligns with multimedia principles) (“Language & Culture”, [2020](#)). Due to the complex tonal nature of Thai, learning the language requires significantly more cognitive abilities and thus, exercises the brain more, improving the flexibility of the brain and benefiting learners’ cognition, as well as reducing the chance of neurological diseases as well (“Top 5 Reasons Why...”, [2023](#)).

1.3 Theoretical Framework (DCT and MLT)

A large part of language learning involves cognitive abilities and the ability of the brain to pick up information (memory retention and recall). First proposed by Paivio in 1971, DCT assumes that learners have two coding systems that work interchangeably with each other to improve recall. One of the systems (verbal system) deals with the linguistic information in units called “logogens”; the other system (non-verbal/visual system) deals with visual information in units called “imagens.” The systems work unconsciously and function separately but interact with each other to result in better processing and memory recall (Kanellopoulou et al. [2019](#)). When watching a drama, according to DCT, the visual image of the audio (the subtitles) are processed in the visual system while the audio (a foreign language) is processed in the verbal system, creating multiple pathways to encode vocabulary and thus, improving language learning. Meanwhile, MLT assumes, based on several past research studies conducted by Mayer and others, that visual aids accompanied with written text reduces cognitive load (Mayer [2002](#)). This theory acts in dramas and subtitles because subtitles are estimated to have a significant impact to the cognitive load audience experience; thus, with this theory, subtitles can actually lower cognitive load (even if it requires both listening and reading) because there is visual information

supplementing the audio. Therefore, both MLT and DCT imply that subtitles help make language learning more efficient and lower the strain placed on learners.

1.4 *Gap*

Much of the current research on subtitles as a vocabulary tool for language learning observes that subtitles have generally positive effects on vocabulary acquisition and, although less studied, comprehension. For instance, Aydin Yildiz (a Ph.D. Student) study observed the impact of subtitles compared to no subtitles on vocabulary of English learners in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) intermediate at a Turkish University; he concluded that bi-modal subtitle group performed significantly better and that watching entertainment content “with the target language subtitles can be useful in the development of the vocabulary acquisition.” (Aydin Yildiz, [2017](#)) Considering past studies that show subtitles as beneficial to vocabulary acquisition and comprehension, Baranowska conducted a study to understand the impacts of subtitle types on cognitive load and if that played a role in learning; she discovered that cognitive load is significantly reduced if the subtitles are in the learners language more than the target language, providing a varying perspective from Yildiz’s findings (Baranowska [2020](#)). This connects to MLT because it further supports the implication that, according to MLT, subtitles would benefit language learning by lowering cognitive load. Adding a varying perspective to the past research studies, another study conducted with a French-speaking population learning English found that between the different viewing formats, there was no difference in cognitive load but results were still beneficial to learning, implying that native language (context) can impact outcome and potentially contradict MLT (Pannatier & B´etrancour, 2024).

Branching off of the previous studies, to understand the impact of different subtitles and if subtitles are still beneficial but with Chinese EFL learners of different ages, Tina Wang results showed dual subtitles benefit one class group (she tested various university class groups with different ages) and have no difference on the other (Wang, [2019](#)). She concluded that different types of subtitles worked better for different age groups, suggesting that subtitles may not be beneficial for all contexts and that results can potentially contradict DCT. Recognizing these varying results, Rong Wei and Lin Fan (published, peer-reviewed authors) conducted a literature review on the different types of on-screen texts and their impact on L2 vocabulary learning. The authors found that a significant number of the studies focused on one native language family (neglecting other language families) and questioned if the distance between target and native language affects outcomes (Wei & Fan, [2022](#)).

While the benefits of subtitles have been displayed in various studies (contexts), there has not yet been substantial research on if subtitles are beneficial to language learning to a beginner population learning a tonal language, such as Thai, in a high school environment. Moreover, Thai and English language families are considered far in linguistic distance and thus, offering another layer as to the importance of replicating the study but with different languages and age groups. Most studies focus on the impacts on an older age range (not high schoolers) with a non-tonal language (usually English). Replicating and furthering past research (by altering contextual constraints) is crucial to supporting the generalizability and robustness of cognitive language learning theories (DCT and MLT). Thus, when considering the effectiveness of subtitled dramas as a tonal language learning tool in high school, it begs the question: How does the presence of subtitles during Thai drama viewing affect vocabulary acquisition, of the Thai

language, and the overall comprehension, of the drama scene, in Central Orlando high school students, considering the multimedia learning theory (MLT) and the dual coding theory (DCT)?

Methodology

2.1 Hypothesis

After looking at the relationship between cognitive learning theories (Dual Coding Theory and Multimedia Learning Theory) and learning languages, the researcher hypothesized that exposure to the drama with English captions (subtitled by GMMTV official Youtube Channel) will show higher comprehension of the drama scene and improved vocabulary test accuracy (measured by comparing results of non subtitles google forms and subtitled google forms) than exposure to the drama without english captions. According to MLT and DCT, learning a language is more efficient with visual and audio aids because it allows for the brain to receive supporting stimuli from two senses to enhance understanding (MLT) and code of both logogens and imagens to improve memory retention of language vocabulary (DCT).

2.2 Design

This study employs a mixed-method quasi-experimental research design, taking inspiration from another study who utilized a pre and post test group of collegiate students to determine the influence of subtitles on cognitive load and language acquisition. (Anjana et al. [2024](#)) The quasi experimental research design has several benefits in the realm of language learning due to its ability to gauge aspects of learning a language by its respective methods. For

example, qualitative research on language learning supports motivation, participants' attitudes toward learning, and retention; on the other hand, quantitative research on language acquisition supports theories on efficiency and statistical evidence of memory recall. On the other hand, quantitative data collected in this study will be analyzed to conclude whether subtitles improved Thai language vocabulary (test scores for pre and post test for both subtitle and non-subtitle groups will be analyzed). The collected data provides a comprehensive overview on the impact of subtitles on learning Thai and allows for the findings to be interpreted in the context of cognitive theories (DCT & MLT).

2.3 Sampling

A convenience sampling method and volunteering sampling method was used, which collected a number of high school students in a central Orlando area high school. Convenience sampling is a nonprobability sampling technique in which subjects are chosen by accessibility to researchers. By using convenience sampling, the researcher is able to easily and cheaply obtain valuable participants without controlling requirements in variables (ensures that researcher observes the natural influence of subtitles on learning). The researcher utilized common school platforms (such as Teams) and word of mouth to spread general and procedural information on the study in order to obtain participants. However, due to the use of convenience sampling for primary participant collection, this poses the presence of observer bias and selection bias in study findings. (Neuman, [2014](#)) Furthermore, the volunteer sampling method can also skew results due to the motivation of participating in the study playing a role in participant performance. The use

of this sampling method aligns with the quasi experimental method because the researcher did not focus on controlling other variables of participants other than age and Thai experience.

Participants were taken from a high school age range (14 - 18 years) due to the lack of studies exploring subtitle impact on adolescents. Other than the restricted age range, the only other inclusion criteria is that participants must be enrolled in the same Central Orlando High School as the research; this adds to data interpretation as the cognitive theories are now put in a different context, which allows the researcher to evaluate the hypothesis that the theories present (subtitles benefit language learning). The majority of literature focused on language learning efficiency and subtitles are centered around its impact on college students familiar with the language itself. For example, a study conducted by Maria Pannatier and Mireille B´etrancourt observed the impact of English subtitles on a nonbilingual French population. Although this study focused on beginner English learners, the median age among the 120 participants (22.3 years) is significantly higher than the high school age range. (Pannatier & B´etrancourt [2023](#)) By using a convenience sampling method, the researcher collected 60 participants all within the 15 - 17 age range. Participants, although not exactly specified or isolated for, are all beginner Thai language learners, which further contributes to answering the research question, analyzing the impact of subtitles on true beginners, and assessing whether entertainment content with subtitles can be an effective introduction to language learning.

2.4 Experimental Procedure

Before the experiment, experimental materials (Non-Subtitle Tests and Subtitle Tests) were dispensed to all participants and participants were given instructions to not open the forms until the experiment was under way. During the initial stage of the experiment, participants are gathered in a single classroom with a smartboard displaying the drama (on the YouTube platform) without any ads present or subtitles turned on. The teacher monitoring the classroom was then instructed to inform the students to fill out the first questionnaire in the Non-Subtitle Test google form. Once the first section was completed by all students, the teacher played “[Eng Sub] I Love ‘A Lot Of’ You รัก มาก เหนือ | EP.1 [1/4]” on Youtube (after skipping the drama’s introductory song) until completion of the video. The students were then instructed to complete the post-test (section 2) of Non-Subtitle Test Form.

After taking a short (less than 2 minute break). Students were asked to complete the first section of the Subtitle Test google form and not move on to the next section. After completion of the first questionnaire, the teacher then played the same video (“[Eng Sub] I Love ‘A Lot Of’ You รัก มาก เหนือ | EP.1 [1/4]” on Youtube) until completion with the GMMTV company providing YouTube subtitles. Once video was watched til completion, the students were then asked to complete the last section of the Subtitle Test (section 2) before ending the experiment. The experiment was repeated in the same classroom with the same proctoring teacher for 3 class periods (earning a total of 60 responses on the Google Forms).

2.5 Ethical Considerations

Throughout the duration of data collection (other than school email collected for participation purposes by the Google Forms), no personal identifying information was collected. Additionally, in both the Non-Subtitle and Subtitle Test Forms, a student consent form was attached to the beginning of the form. The consent form without taking any personal information asked for confirmation and willingness by the participant to partake in the experiment. Furthermore, no invasive procedures were performed and no part of the questionnaire questioned participant mental or physical health. The only people that have access to the recorded information are the proctoring teacher and the researcher, which prevents personal privacy breaches from occurring. Moreover, the research proposal was IRB approved before data collection started.

2.6 Statistical Analysis Method

Quantitative data from experimental procedures will be collected and analyzed through the use of score distributions, means, and standard deviations (this will be done for each condition in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of performance), which will be displayed in graphs. To test the hypothesis, the researcher will conduct a paired-sample t-test (compare non-subtitle v. subtitle condition). This test will help support the hypothesis because it can accurately show the comparison between the two choices and the statistical difference in both vocabulary acquisition and scene comprehension in the same group of students. Furthermore, the researcher will perform a repeated measures ANOVA test to compare the mean scores across all three main conditions (pre test non subtitle vs post test non subtitle vs post test subtitle) to demonstrate performance over time. The statistical significance will be set at $p <$

0.05. This aligns with MLT and DCT because performance changes are measured due to increased input channels.

Results

Thai Vocabulary Results Descriptives Table

Descriptives ▼

	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
PRE_NOSUB_TOTAL	57	1.509	1.136	0.150	0.753
PRE_SUB_TEST	57	2.316	1.325	0.176	0.572
POST_NOSUB_TOTAL	57	2.158	1.222	0.162	0.566
POST_SUB_TEST	57	2.789	1.612	0.213	0.578

Paired Samples T-Test for Vocabulary Test Results

Paired Samples T-Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p	Cohen's d	SE Cohen's d	95% CI for Cohen's d	
							Lower	Upper
PRE_NOSUB_TOTAL	- PRE_SUB_TEST	-3.985	56	< .001	-0.528	0.175	-0.803	-0.248
PRE_NOSUB_TOTAL	- POST_NOSUB_TOTAL	-3.391	56	.001	-0.449	0.170	-0.720	-0.175
PRE_SUB_TEST	- POST_SUB_TEST	-2.088	56	.041	-0.277	0.156	-0.540	-0.011
POST_NOSUB_TOTAL	- POST_SUB_TEST	-2.776	56	.007	-0.368	0.163	-0.634	-0.098

Paired Samples T-Test Descriptive Plots

3.1 Hypothesis Test

Results from the paired samples t-test supports the main hypothesis of subtitle exposure resulting in improved language acquisition because it shows a significant statistical improvement in scores between the post vocabulary test in non-subtitled condition and the post vocabulary test in subtitled condition. A paired sample t-test revealed that participants scored higher on vocabulary post test in subtitled condition ($M = 2.789$, $SD = 1.612$) compared to vocabulary post test in non-subtitled condition ($M = 2.158$, $SD = 1.222$), indicate small to moderate impact of subtitle exposure in vocabulary acquisition through dramas. The t-test also indicated a p value of less than 0.05 (specifically 0.007 as highest) and confidence interval calculated shown in t-test doesn't include 0 which supports data being statistically significant. The negative t value indicates the t-test subtracted non subtitled condition scores from condition scores, meaning that subtitled condition test scores are higher than non subtitled test scores. The impact can be quantified as small to moderate as the absolute value of Cohen's d is around 0.368, meaning it is not large but it is also not insignificant. Visual analysis of Q-Q plots (for each variable pair in paired sample t-test) show that normality of assumption is satisfied.

3.2 Secondary Analysis Tests

When looking at the paired samples t-test, comparing the mean test scores within each condition (comparing vocabulary pre test for non subtitled condition compared to vocabulary post test for non subtitled condition and comparing vocabulary pre test for subtitled condition

compared to vocabulary post test for subtitled condition) revealed that significant statistical improvement occurred in both the non-subtitled condition and the subtitled condition. While acquisition improved in both conditions, the presence of subtitles in the subtitle condition allowed for an increased improvement in vocabulary test scores and thus, supports the hypothesis that subtitles can help improve language learning through vocabulary acquisition to a noticeable extent. Comparing the baselines for both conditions (vocabulary pre test for non subtitled condition compared to vocabulary pre test for subtitled condition) indicate significant difference. This implies that baseline levels for both subtitle conditions are not the same, which could support the hypothesis of time and prior knowledge or experience (through the experiment) as a reason for the acquisition of Thai vocabulary instead of subtitle presence.

3.3 Repeated Measures ANOVA Test

In order to test the progression of language learning over time, a repeated measures ANOVA test was performed. The ANOVA test was performed with a factor of time and 4 points in time: level 1 - Pre Test for Non Subtitled Condition; level 2 - Post Test for Non Subtitled Condition; level 3 - Pre Test for Subtitled Condition; level 4 - Post Test for Subtitled Condition. While ANOVA assesses the overall difference between the 4 conditions given, the post-hoc tests done with ANOVA assess where the specific differences in data are by checking pairs or the 4 levels imputed. Since the chance of false positives rises with comparing a large number of variable pairs, Bonferroni adjustment was accounted for in the test to make results “safer”, by making the p values calculated more strict and controlling error in analysis.

ANOVA Condition Descriptive Tables

Descriptives ▼

Time	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
Level 1	57	1.509	1.136	0.150	0.753
Level 2	57	2.158	1.222	0.162	0.566
Level 3	57	2.316	1.325	0.176	0.572
Level 4	57	2.789	1.612	0.213	0.578

Repeated Measures ANOVA Result Tables

Within Subjects Effects

Cases	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2
Time	47.89	3	15.965	13.01	< .001	0.189
Residuals	206.11	168	1.227			

Note. Type III Sum of Squares

Between Subjects Effects ▼

Cases	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Residuals	193.5	56	3.456		

Note. Type III Sum of Squares

Repeated Measures ANOVA Descriptive Plot

Post Hoc Test Results

Post Hoc Comparisons – Time ▼

		Mean Difference	SE	df	t	P _{bonf}
Level 1	Level 2	-0.649	0.191	56	-3.391	.008
	Level 3	-0.807	0.202	56	-3.985	.001
	Level 4	-1.281	0.225	56	-5.694	< .001
Level 2	Level 3	-0.158	0.164	56	-0.964	1.000
	Level 4	-0.632	0.228	56	-2.776	.045
Level 3	Level 4	-0.474	0.227	56	-2.088	.248

Note. P-value adjusted for comparing a family of 6 estimates.

The Repeated Measures ANOVA test indicates the F-value is 13.01, a strong value, and that data is statistically significant according to p-value. To elaborate, the p-value shown with ANOVA (< .001) stipulates that the chance of differences occurring randomly is a significantly small number, less than 0.1%. Since the rarity of the differences being made from a random occurrence is so notable, the null hypothesis that subtitle presence is not related to language acquisition can be rejected as there is a difference between all conditions. The findings from the ANOVA repeated measure test thus support the hypothesis that subtitle presence when viewing dramas improve vocabulary acquisition of the drama language and comprehension. Furthermore, the effect size (η^2), which is 0.189, being a large number shows that time/condition played a noteworthy role in the differences in test scores across all 4 levels or conditions. Additionally, Mauchly's Test indicated that the assumption of sphericity was met in the data. Expanding on post-hoc test results, the post hoc comparisons with Bonferroni correction show that Level 1 had significant differences with every level, specifically Level 1 was lower than level 2, level 3, and level 4. Post hoc comparisons also showed significant difference between level 2 and level 4, although not the most considerable statistical difference between levels, but no significant difference between the other levels.

Conclusion

This study explores the relationship between subtitles and language learning in relation to cognitive theories (especially Dual Coding Theory and Multimedia Theory). Specifically, the study observes if the presence of subtitles when viewing Thai entertainment content influences language learning in a positive way. By assessing language learning in high school students with the Thai language (tonal language), the study is able to address previous gaps in research pertaining to language learning. For example, a study done by Rong Wei and Lin Fan concluded that both visual and auditory stimuli makes learning more efficient; however, the study's participants consisted of an older range than high school students and utilized a language (that is not tonal, unlike Thai) (Wei & Fan, [2022](#)). Thus, this study plans to explore the hypothesis that watching the drama with subtitles will show higher comprehension of the drama scene and improved vocabulary test accuracy than exposure to the drama without english captions.

Results of this study show that the mean accuracy of the vocabulary test after the drama with subtitles was statistically higher than the mean accuracy of the vocabulary test after the drama. This supports the hypothesis that exposure to the drama with english captions will show higher comprehension of the drama scene and improved vocabulary test accuracy than exposure to the drama without english captions can be supported by the data collected. Assessing the results obtained from the repeated measures ANOVA test, the null hypothesis that subtitle presence is not related to language acquisition can be rejected as there is a significant difference between all conditions. The ANOVA test and the paired measures T-Test results (plus post Hoc Test results) also supports the cognitive theories of DCT and MLT as data shows both visual (subtitles) and auditory (dialogue) stimuli result in better comprehension and language learning

in a new context (Thai language learning in high school students). Specifically, MLT suggests that visual aids and written language reduce cognitive load, leading to increased learning; the results support this because the visual aids (the drama) and written language (subtitles) show increased learning, although the impact of subtitles on cognitive load is not supported by the results. Similarly, DCT suggests that the coding pathways of visual and auditory pathways work separately to create multiple learning pathways, facilitating effective learning through increased memory encoding. The results from the paired measures T-Test and the post Hoc test show improved accuracy over different conditions and over time respectively for the vocabulary tests (vocabulary relies on memory), with specific growth in accuracy after watching the drama with subtitles, supporting the view that subtitles are in alignment with DCT and promote effective learning.

4.1 Implications and Limitations

The conclusions derived from this study suggest that using subtitles as a form of instruction (especially the inclusion of subtitles when listening/watching foreign media) can enhance foreign language learning in schools. The statistical differences in mean accuracy scores of the vocabulary tests over the different conditions display the usefulness of subtitles as a learning tool in unfamiliar linguistic contexts. The findings from the study align with DCT (suggests that information presented through visual and auditory pathways improve memory coding and result in more efficient learning) and MLT (suggests that combining multiple stimuli when learning improves efficiency to a significant extent). In an educational context, the alignment of the study's findings and cognitive theories prove the beneficial effects of subtitled

foreign media (such as foreign language dramas) in improving language learning efficiency and supplementing independent learning environments (provides diversity in learning experiences). Looking into broader implications, the findings of this study (especially the fact that multiple sensory stimuli motivate learning more efficiency and effectively) also support the potential of multimedia learning tools to improve accessibility for people who face learning disabilities or have other sensory disorders. The alignment of results with DCT and MLT predictions in the context of tonal language acquisition by adolescents suggest broader generalizations of the theory than they were originally intended, though the study poses limitations that suggest a preliminary, rather than definitive, conclusion.

Although the study is shown to have various implications, the findings should also be interpreted with several limitations. The study was performed amongst a specific group of high school students which limits the generalizability of the data collected. Furthermore, the participants of the study may be exposed to various types of bias. The nature of this study requires simultaneous understanding of the visual drama and captions, along with Thai audio, inviting familiarity bias, as students who watch subtitled content regularly may have a stronger integration pathways, leading to overstating of the cognitive theories in beginners and the impact of subtitles on language learning. The design of this study also promotes a phenomenon called the carryover effect: due to the repetition of content, participants may have had higher scores in the vocabulary test due to retention and re-exposure rather than pure subtitle driven integration, which could limit the claims relating to DCT and MLT. The participants might also have researcher bias (researcher's prior interest in subtitle-based learning may have influenced participants' reaction to content presented) and demand characteristic bias (participants know

hypothesis or understand point of experiment and unconsciously adjust behavior to align with their beliefs), which could have influenced the results of the study (Bonneau, [2023](#)). Therefore, these biases and additional factors (that come with the experiment being held in the real world) imply that the conclusions of this study, relating to subtitle-based language learning, are not conclusive and definitive.

4.2 Future Directions

Future research could take this study a step further by exploring the cognitive impact of subtitles on participants learning Thai. Studies could also explore the long-term consequences of subtitle-based instruction on learning foreign languages and acquisition of cultural knowledge through subtitled media. Studies could further explore the influence of different types of subtitles on effective vocabulary retention and scene comprehension. Furthermore, future researchers could explore how subtitled-based language learning can influence social media consumption and cultural understanding (including pronunciation and listening comprehension). To improve generalization, future research could include more diverse age groups, ethnic groups, and geographic regions. Finally, the findings of the study give rise to the exploration of different forms of media being used as modes of instruction in classrooms focused on language learning education, improving learning diversity and aiding people in need of more effective, efficient learning.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Institutional Review Board Form

Institutional Review Board

Application for Approval of AP Research Project

Research Question	How does the presence of subtitles during Thai drama viewing affect vocabulary acquisition, of the Thai language, and the overall comprehension, of the drama scene, in Central Orlando high school students, considering the multimedia learning theory (MLT) and the dual coding theory (DCT)?
Describe Project, Purpose, Gap and Significance: Briefly describe (a) the project or study and if appropriate, (b) what human participants will experience during the proposed study or project. Explain the purpose of the project, what gap in the body of knowledge your research will address. and the significance of your research.	The project will involve students watching the first episode (part 1/4) of Thai drama "I love a lot of you" and answering a questionnaire. This addresses the prevailing gap of how entertaining media can influence high schoolers ability to learn languages through the lens of two cognitive theories. Furthermore, this project puts the dual coding theory and multimedia learning theory into a new context, which can significantly aid in understanding of cognitive pathways. By doing so, I will be able to collect data on how subtitles can impact understanding, which can be used further second language learning and aid in language development overall.

Subjects from special/vulnerable populations (place X) If none, mark "none of the above"	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Children under 18
<input type="checkbox"/>	Economically disadvantaged
<input type="checkbox"/>	People with intellectual disabilities
<input type="checkbox"/>	Senior citizens/elderly
<input type="checkbox"/>	Prisoners
<input type="checkbox"/>	People with physical disabilities
<input type="checkbox"/>	None of the above

Research subjects in the following categories (place X)	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OSS high school students
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other high school students
<input type="checkbox"/>	General public
<input type="checkbox"/>	Faculty
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adults over 18
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (specify)
<input type="checkbox"/>	None of the above

Confidentiality	Yes X	No X
Does the project/study involve collection of data that identifies individuals? (i.e., name, student number, etc., attached to survey, interview, databases, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Will individually identifiable data be shared with anyone (i.e, conference presentation, report for funding source, published article, etc.)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Will participants' privacy and personal information be protected?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Are participants being offered any incentives to participate, such as money, extra credit, etc.?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Need for voluntary consent forms	Yes X	No X
Is participation in the project or study voluntary for individuals participating? <i>If Yes, include a voluntary consent form in Appendices.</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix 2: Non-Subtitle Test Form

Non-Subtitle Tests

SECTION 1

This experiment discusses this research question: How does the presence of subtitles during Thai drama viewing affect vocabulary acquisition, of the Thai language, and the overall comprehension, of the drama scene, in Central Orlando high school students, considering the multimedia learning theory (MLT) and the dual coding theory (DCT)?

For more background, The study aims to determine whether the presence of English subtitles in Thai drama viewing affects high school students' conceptual understanding (in terms of overall comprehension and tonal vocabulary acquisition). Thai is not very popular in our school and not as studied in terms of language learning; thus, this study plans to see if the context presented in this experiment can effectively aid tonal language learning. Another goal is to see if the cognitive load presented when viewing the drama is enough to leave a substantial effect on the participants, in relation to Mayer's MLT (suggests that multiple input channels can result in better learning due to DCT). To elaborate, this study also interprets these results in the DCT, which states that there are two input channels (verbal channel and nonverbal channel) that work together in the brain to aid in better comprehension of the input. Therefore, by viewing a Thai drama with English subtitles, the study observes if dual coding (exposure to subtitles, drama scene, Thai audio) can aid in scene comprehension and tonal language meaning.
mm.0520@student.orlandoscience.net Switch account

* Indicates required question

Email*

As a participant, you will only be required to answer the questions honestly for the surveys taken before and after each video clip. While the video clip is playing, as a participant, all you have to do is watch the video to the best of your ability.

If you do not agree to participate in this experiment, then please type out "I do not wish to participate in this experiment.". If you agree to participate, then please retype the following statement below:

"I voluntarily consent to participating in this experiment and agree to fill out the following questionnaire."*

What is your age? (numerically)*

NON-SUBTITLED Pre-TEST

Student participation in an experiment determining the relationship between subtitles and language learning when watching Dramas

You will take this test prior to watching the non subtitled video clip of a Thai Drama and will be asked to complete this test to the best of your abilities.

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language (audio)? If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I have heard Thai and I am very comfortable with it (very familiar) (5)

I have heard Thai but not as comfortable with it (4)

I have heard Thai and am familiar with it (3)

I have barely heard Thai before (2)

I have not heard Thai (1)

Other:

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language characters (writing)?

If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I am very familiar with Thai characters (5)

I am very familiar with Thai characters but to a lesser extent (4)

I am familiar with Thai characters (3)

I have seen the Thai characters before (2)

I have not seen Thai characters before (1)

Other:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/123z1v1Wnxc9qpA8fkSBHWqGiCQ9ZGALP/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 5)

ไม, mai

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Yes

No

Thank you

Of Course

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-WeOgOrqMSDfvrVU7w5aAv4mukrITDLZ/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 3)

ผู้หญิง, phu ying

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Welcome

Of Course

Woman

Man

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Yjid4-nVum8f93UaGv3KtO5SM7iNDJy3/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 2)

สวัสดี, Sawasdee kha/khap

What does this word/phrase mean?*

4 5 6

Hello

I would love to

Of Course

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WXmLDSXhRU8jW595Ot1Q5bMoFYmhV7ps/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 1)

ขอบคุณ, Khop Khun kha/khap

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Hello

Thank you

Your Welcome

No thanks

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BQwmwrwGc9n7Jst7cpVCxYzO439xwGjl/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 6)

หนึ่งสองสาม, neung song sam

What does this word/phrase mean?*

4 5 6

1 2 3

6 7 8

8 9 10

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1o5I--XTXP3ayKoT2eE2cfn-sOldCKwbp/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 4)

ผู้ชาย, phu chai

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Man

Woman

1 2 3

Thank you

How well do you think you will understand the content shown? (1: will not understand at all; 5: will understand perfectly)*

1 2 3 4 5

Do you enjoy watching videos with or without subtitles? Do you usually watch dramas (or videos) with subtitles? (max 2 sentences)*

What are your opinions on subtitles? Are they beneficial? Are they harmful? (max 2 sentences)*

NON-SUBTITLED Post-TEST

Student participation in an experiment determining the relationship between subtitles and language learning when watching Dramas

You will take this test after watching the non subtitled video clip of a Thai Drama and will be asked to complete this test to the best of your abilities.

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language (audio)? (other than video just shown) If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I have heard Thai and I am very comfortable with it (very familiar) (5)

I have heard Thai but not as comfortable with it (4)

I have heard Thai and am familiar with it (3)

I have barely heard Thai before (2)

I have not heard Thai (1)

Other: _____

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language characters (writing)?

If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I am very familiar with Thai characters (5)

I am very familiar with Thai characters but to a lesser extent (4)

I am familiar with Thai characters (3)

I have seen the Thai characters before (2)

I have not seen Thai characters before (1)

Other: _____

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Yjid4-nVum8f93UaGv3KtO5SM7iNDJy3/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 2)

สวัสดี, Sawasdee kha/khap

What does this word/phrase mean?*

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<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-WeOgOrqMSDfvrVU7w5aAv4mukrlTDLZ/view?usp=sharing>

(audio file for thai file 3)

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What does this word/phrase mean?*

Welcome

Of Course

Woman

Man

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/123z1v1Wnxc9qpA8fkSBHWqGiCQ9ZGALP/view?usp=sharing>

(audio file for thai file 5)

ไม่, mai

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Yes

No

Thank you

Of Course

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1o5I--XTXP3ayKoT2eE2cfn-sOldCKwbp/view?usp=sharing>

(audio file for thai file 4)

ผู้ชาย, phu chai

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Man

Woman

1 2 3

Thank you

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BQwmwrwGc9n7Jst7cpVCxYzO439xwGjl/view?usp=sharing>

(audio file for thai file 6)

หนึ่งสองสาม, neung song sam

What does this word/phrase mean?*

4 5 6

1 2 3

6 7 8

8 9 10

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WXmLDSXhRU8jW595Ot1Q5bMoFYmhV7ps/view?usp=sharing> (audio file for thai file 1)

ขอบคุณ, Khop Khun kha/khap

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Hello

Thank you

Your Welcome

No thanks

How well do you believe you understood the content shown? (1: did not understand at all; 5: understood perfectly)*

1 2 3 4 5

What do you think happened in the content shown? (summary of scene in drama) (max 2 sentences)*

Do you think subtitles would have benefited your situation (2 sentence max)?*

Appendix 3: Subtitle Test Form

Subtitles Tests

SECTION 1

This experiment discusses this research question: How does the presence of subtitles during Thai drama viewing affect vocabulary acquisition, of the Thai language, and the overall comprehension, of the drama scene, in Central Orlando high school students, considering the multimedia learning theory (MLT) and the dual coding theory (DCT)?

For more background, The study aims to determine whether the presence of English subtitles in Thai drama viewing affect high school students' conceptual understanding (in terms of overall comprehension and tonal vocabulary acquisition). Thai is not very popular in our school and not as studied in terms of language learning; thus, this study plans to see if the context presented in this experiment can effectively aid tonal language learning. Another goal is to see if the cognitive load presented when viewing the drama is enough to leave a substantial effect on the participants, in relation to Mayer's MLT (suggests that multiple input channels can result in better learning due to DCT). To elaborate, this study also interprets these results in the DCT, which states that there are two input channels (verbal channel and nonverbal channel) that work

together in the brain to aid in better comprehension of the input. Therefore, by viewing a Thai drama with English subtitles, the study observes if dual coding (exposure to subtitles, drama scene, Thai audio) can aid in scene comprehension and tonal language meaning.
mm.0520@student.orlandoscience.net Switch account

* Indicates required question

Email*

As a participant, you will only be required to answer the questions honestly for the surveys taken before and after each video clip. While the video clip is playing, as a participant, all you have to do is watch the video to the best of your ability.

If you do not agree to participate in this experiment, then please type out "I do not wish to participate in this experiment.". If you agree to participate, then please retype the following statement below:

"I voluntarily consent to participating in this experiment and agree to fill out the following questionnaire."*

What is your age? (numerically)*

SUBTITLED Pre-TEST

Student participation in an experiment determining the relationship between subtitles and language learning when watching Dramas

These sets of questionnaires will be administered after the 5 minute break.

After the 5 minute break, participants will be asked to fill out the Pre Test 2, then watch the first ¼ part of ep 1 of "I love A lot of You" Thai drama with subtitles.

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language (audio)? (other than video seen) If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I have heard Thai and I am very comfortable with it (very familiar) (5)

I have heard Thai but not as comfortable with it (4)

I have heard Thai and am familiar with it (3)

I have barely heard Thai before (2)

I have not heard Thai (1)

Other: _____

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language characters (writing)? (other than test taken) If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I am very familiar with Thai characters (5)

I am very familiar with Thai characters but to a lesser extent (4)

I am familiar with Thai characters (3)

I have seen the Thai characters before (2)

I have not seen Thai characters before (1)

Other: _____

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WXmLDSXhRU8jW595Ot1Q5bMoFYmhV7ps/view?usp=sharing>

ng (audio file for thai file 1)

ขอบคุณ, Khop Khun kha/khap

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Hello

Thank you

Your Welcome

No thanks

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Yjid4-nVum8f93UaGv3KtO5SM7iNDJy3/view?usp=sharing>

(audio file for thai file 2)

สวัสดี, Sawasdee kha/khap

What does this word/phrase mean?*

4 5 6

Hello

I would love to

Of Course

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-WeOgOrqMSDfvrVU7w5aAv4mukrITDLZ/view?usp=sharing>

(audio file for thai file 3)

ผู้หญิง, phu ying

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Welcome

Of Course

Woman

Man

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1o5I--XTXP3ayKoT2eE2cfn-sOldCKwbp/view?usp=sharing>

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ผู้ชาย, phu chai

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Man

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1 2 3

Thank you

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/123z1v1Wnxc9qpA8fkSBHWqGiCQ9ZGALP/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 5)

ไม่, mai

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Yes

No

Thank you

Of Course

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1BQwmwrwGc9n7Jst7cpVCxYzO439xwGjl/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 6)

หนึ่งสองสาม, neung song sam

What does this word/phrase mean?*

4 5 6

1 2 3

6 7 8

8 9 10

How comfortable are you with Thai? (1: not comfortable; 5: very comfortable)*

1 2 3 4 5

Do you believe that subtitles are beneficial to understanding a drama scene (2 sentence max)?*

Do you believe that subtitles can help learn Thai vocabulary (2 sentence max)?*

What is your predicted improvement on the Vocab section? (answer in predicted score/6)*

SUBTITLED Post-TEST

Student participation in an experiment determining the relationship between subtitles and language learning when watching Dramas

You will take this test after watching the subtitled video clip of a Thai Drama and will be asked to complete this test to the best of your abilities.

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language (audio)? (other than video just shown) If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I have heard Thai and I am very comfortable with it (very familiar) (5)

I have heard Thai but not as comfortable with it (4)

I have heard Thai and am familiar with it (3)

I have barely heard Thai before (2)

I have not heard Thai (1)

Other: _____

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language characters (writing)? If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.*

I am very familiar with Thai characters (5)

I am very familiar with Thai characters but to a lesser extent (4)

I am familiar with Thai characters (3)

I have seen the Thai characters before (2)

I have not seen Thai characters before (1)

Other: _____

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Yjid4-nVum8f93UaGv3KtO5SM7iNDJy3/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 2)

สวัสดี, Sawasdee kha/khap

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Of Course

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-WeOgOrqMSDfvrVU7w5aAv4mukrlTDLZ/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 3)

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Woman

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<https://drive.google.com/file/d/123z1v1Wnxc9qpA8fkSBHWqGiCQ9ZGALP/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 5)

ไม่, mai

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Yes

No
Thank you
Of Course

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1o5I--XTXP3ayKoT2eE2cfn-sOldCKwbp/view?usp=sharing>
(audio file for thai file 4)

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หนึ่งสองสาม, neung song sam

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(audio file for thai file 1)

ขอบคุณ, Khop Khun kha/khap

What does this word/phrase mean?*

Hello

Thank you

Your Welcome

No thanks

How well do you believe you understood the content shown? (1: did not understand at all; 5: understood perfectly)*

1 2 3 4 5

What do you think happened in the content shown? (summary of scene in drama) (max 2 sentences)*

Do you believe that subtitles can help learn Thai vocabulary (2 sentence max)?*

How beneficial were the subtitles in understanding the scene and Thai vocab? (1: not beneficial; 5: very beneficial)

1 2 3 4 5

Did having the subtitles when watching the content make the content more enjoyable? (1: didn't make it enjoyable; 5: made it very enjoyable)

1 2 3 4 5

Appendix 4: NON-SUBTITLED Test Point Distribution

Average 3.67 / 12 points	Median 3 / 12 points	Range 0 - 8 points
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Total points distribution

Appendix 5: NON-SUBTITLED Pre-Test Previous Thai Knowledge

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language (audio)? If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.

64 responses

- I have heard Thai and I am very comfortable with it (very familiar) (5)
- I have heard Thai but not as comfortable with it (4)
- I have heard Thai and am familiar with it (3)
- I have barely heard Thai before (2)
- I have not heard Thai (1)

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language characters (writing)? If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.

64 responses

- I am very familiar with Thai characters (5)
- I am very familiar with Thai characters but to a lesser extent (4)
- I am familiar with Thai characters (3)
- I have seen the Thai characters before (2)
- I have not seen Thai characters before (1)

Appendix 6: NON-SUBTITLED Pre-Test Participant Perception of Concept

How well do you think you will understand the content shown? (1: will not understand at all; 5: will understand perfectly)

64 responses

Appendix 7: SUBTITLED Test Point Distribution

Average
5.3 / 12 points

Median
5 / 12 points

Range
0 - 12 points

Total points distribution

Appendix 8: SUBTITLED Pre-Test Previous Thai Knowledge

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language (audio)? (other than video seen) If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.

60 responses

- I have heard Thai and I am very comfortable with it (very familiar) (5)
- I have heard Thai but not as comfortable with it (4)
- I have heard Thai and am familiar with it (3)
- I have barely heard Thai before (2)
- I have not heard Thai (1)

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language characters (writing)? (other than test taken) If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.

60 responses

- I am very familiar with Thai characters (5)
- I am very familiar with Thai characters but to a lesser extent (4)
- I am familiar with Thai characters (3)
- I have seen the Thai characters before (2)
- I have not seen Thai characters before (1)

Appendix 9: SUBTITLED Predicted Efficiency of Subtitles

What is your predicted improvement on the Vocab section? (answer in predicted score/6)

60 responses

Appendix 10: SUBTITLED Post-Test Previous Thai Knowledge

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language (audio)? (other than video just shown) If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.

60 responses

- I have heard Thai and I am very comfortable with it (very familiar) (5)
- I have heard Thai but not as comfortable with it (4)
- I have heard Thai and am familiar with it (3)
- I have barely heard Thai before (2)
- I have not heard Thai (1)

Do you have prior knowledge about the Thai language characters (writing)? If other is chosen, please elaborate on your thoughts in one sentence.

60 responses

- I am very familiar with Thai characters (5)
- I am very familiar with Thai characters but to a lesser extent (4)
- I am familiar with Thai characters (3)
- I have seen the Thai characters before (2)
- I have not seen Thai characters before (1)

Appendix 11: SUBTITLED Post-Test Participant Perception of Content Understanding

How well do you believe you understood the content shown? (1: did not understand at all; 5: understood perfectly)

60 responses

Appendix 12: SUBTITLED Post-Test Participant Perception of Subtitles

How beneficial were the subtitles in understanding the scene and Thai vocab? (1: not beneficial; 5: very beneficial)

59 responses

Appendix 13: SUBTITLED Post-Test Participant Enjoyment with Subtitles

Did having the subtitles when watching the content make the content more enjoyable? (1: didn't make it enjoyable; 5: made it very enjoyable)

60 responses

Appendix 14: Raw Numerical Data

ID	PRE_NOSUB_TOTAL			POST_NOSUB_TOTAL	PRE_SUB_TEST			POST_SUB_TEST
P01	2	1	1	3				
P02	1	2	3	1				
P03	0	0	0	0				
P04	2	0	1	1				
P05	0	4	1	1				
P06	3	4	4	3				
P07	1	2	5	1				
P08	3	2	2	4				
P09	1	2	2	3				
P10	1	1	3	2				
P11	2	1	1	1				

P12	0	2	1	5
P13	3	4	3	3
P14	1	1	2	1
P15	2	3	2	4
P16	2	5	5	3
P17	3	5	5	4
P18	5	3	3	5
P19	2	4	5	4
P20	2	2	1	2
P21	1	1	0	0
P22	1	1	1	1
P23	2	2	2	4
P24	2	2	2	2
P25	2	3	1	3
P26	3	1	1	1
P27	2	4	3	2
P28	1	0	1	2
P29	1	2	2	1
P30	4	2	4	6
P31	3	1	3	1
P32	4	3	3	5
P33	1	2	1	5
P34	2	4	3	4

P35	1	3	4	1
P36	0	3	1	0
P37	2	2	3	3
P38	1	1	2	1
P39	1	2	3	5
P40	3	2	1	3
P41	1	0	3	4
P42	1	3	3	3
P43	0	2	2	5
P44	1	1	3	3
P45	1	1	1	3
P46	1	2	2	5
P47	1	4	5	5
P48	1	2	4	4
P49	0	1	4	4
P50	2	2	1	6
P51	1	2	1	1
P52	2	3	2	2
P53	0	3	2	4
P54	0	2	2	3
P55	0	1	1	2
P56	1	2	2	2
P57	0	3	3	2